

The importance of engaging in standards setting

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WHY

Benefits

Short-term and long-term benefits and a sustainable competitive advantage by:

- Opportunity to learn and discuss ideas
- Networking for partnership alliances
- To gain recognition in the industry and among customers taking an active/leading role
- Ensure the final standards best meet market and SME needs
- Timely access to knowledge
- Vigilance on future standards & and regulations,
- Eventually influences capacity

Leading

MARKET

CONVENOR

EXPERT

- Reach Consensus
- Administrative Tasks
- Neutrality
- Measuring

¡Thanks!

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SBS Expert

- Convenor ISO TC 307 Blockchain and DLTs WG5

Governance

- Convenor CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain and DLTs WG2 **Environmental Sustainability**
- **Expert ISO TC 279 Innovation Management**
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